

Deliverable 4.4: EURAKNOS visuals and specifications to define the future vision for the e-KRP

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

T4.3: Conceptualization of the future vision for the e-KRP

Summary

Task description: The purpose of this task is to further leverage the EC investments in Thematic Networks and the EURAKNOS project by creating a future vision for the e-KRP. The task will capitalize upon the work of WP2, WP3 and WP4 (T4.1 - T4.2) to provide meaningful insight in the UI, UX and functionalities of the e-KRP in future development iterations, when the e-KRP matures from prototype to production. The task team did this in close collaboration with end-users of the e-KRP by performing user tests, interviews and gathering feedback using the prototype of the e-KRP. The task team worked in close collaboration with TN coordinators (both EURAKNOS partners and other players of the ecosystem).

Results and conclusion: Based on this input, the team created the necessary visuals and specifications to define the future vision for the e-KRP.

Deliverable Number	Work Package
4.4	WP4
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Planned Delivery Date	Actual Delivery Date
31/03/2020	31/03/2020

Type of Deliverable	R	Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)	x
	DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos	
	E	Ethics	

Dissemination Level	PU	Public	
	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

EURAKNOS – Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs: towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

EUREKA – European Knowledge Repository for Best Agricultural Practices

KR – Knowledge Reservoir

TN – Thematic Network

WP – Work Package

UX – User Experience

UI – User Interface

e-KRP – electronic Knowledge Reservoir Platform

PoC – Proof of Concept

1. Introduction

This document describes the work performed within T4.3 regarding the Euraknos visualisation and specifications for the future vision of the e-KRP also referred to as the FarmBook. The deliverables presented in this document are the result of the work conducted in task 4.3 in order to design the user experience (UX) and user interface (UI) for the end-user facing e-KRP. The work is based on the work performed in WP2, WP3, WP4 (T4.1 - T4.2) and WP5 (D5.8: The vision paper), and completes the work described in deliverable D4.3 in which the development of the back-end and front-end of the e-KRP is detailed. A process moving from the creation of wireframes, the gathering of feedback, the creation of mock-ups was used to achieve the Proof of Concept (PoC) of the front-end of the e-KRP presented in this deliverable. Additionally, a digital style guide containing all the information with regards to logo's, fonts and colours to be used in the mock-ups and PoC is presented.

1.1. Context

The development of digital products has evolved over the last decades from a one-shot attempt to create a product which meets the current as-is requirements to a more Agile and iterative methodology where prototypes are created at an early stage and feedback is regularly collected in order to detect the major issues in at the start of the development and only smaller issues need be resolved towards the end.

1.2. Objectives

In order not to lose track of the initial goal of creating an e-KRP, it is imperative to develop a vision for the future platform and accommodate this vision with concrete visuals and specifications in order to challenge assumptions currently held about the concept of the platform as well as detect possible obstacles for development in the future. Additionally, the creation of visuals and specifications through the forms of wireframes, mock-ups and a digital style guide allowed us to collect more insightful feedback from end-users. The method of working from wireframes to a digital style guide is commonly used in the development of digital products as this allows the designer to focus more on the basics of the digital product (e.g. which content has to be presented on where and why) in the beginning of the design process, while later stages of the design process can focus more on how the content is presented (e.g. which colours and visual design).

2. Task members

Table 1. Partners involved in Task 4.3 (in bold the task leaders).

Task	Partner													
	ACTA	IDELE	NAK	UGent	GLZ	USC	AU	PSKW	ARC	AUA	IFA	LFG	RAU	EV ILVO
4.3			X	X						X		X		

3. Wireframes

The low-fidelity wireframes provide a sense of the components on the web pages and how they are arranged. These show components relative in size and position, but don't have any visual design details like images, colours and fonts. D4.3 describes the feedback gathered to the first version of the wireframes of which an example is shown in Figure 1 after which these were updated. The first version of these wireframes can be found in Annex A.

Figure 1. An example of a low-fidelity wireframe

Based on feedback gathered during the Athens consortium meeting (June 2019) and the Paris expert meeting (December 2019) the wireframes were updated by moving away from the concept of using a dashboard or creating a Wikipedia-like library. Through discussions with members of the consortium it was decided to start working more with specific environments dedicated to a particular sector (e.g. forestry) or cross-sectoral theme (e.g. environment) which would allow the user to explore new content within such an environment and allow communities to develop around those environments. Additionally, the platform would focus more on the content and interactions about that content by users and experts through a comments-option linked to each knowledge object presented on the platform. This would allow users to have more structured discussions about specific content and exchange knowledge. In order to allow the content and discussions to be monitored and curated, the decision was made to move towards a Reddit-style moderation model where content and comments can be upvoted and downvoted by registered users only. The option to allow messaging between users or separate groups was abandoned as this could lead to valuable information by users to be kept out of view of the other users not involved in those discussions. Furthermore, the first version of the wireframes paid too much attention to the thematic networks, which have a limited lifespan, rather than the community which could be developed around specific sectors or cross-sectoral themes. News and events were also removed to allow the user to focus more on the knowledge objects available on

the platform, within sector-specific or cross-sectoral specific environments the most recent items would be displayed first, replacing the news-function.

The updated wireframes of which an example is shown in Figure 2 provided a basis for discussion between the coordination team, back-end developers, front-end developers, UX-designers and user researchers before moving on to the mock-ups. The wireframes can be found in Annex B.

Figure 2. An example of a low-fidelity wireframe

Additional discussions with consortium members allowed us to refine the design of the platform to focus more on the presented knowledge objects in the mock-ups presented in chapter 4 by focusing directly on the latest knowledge objects uploaded per sector or cross-sectoral theme. Discussions around the types of subcategories, and the impact this would have on the data-annotation process suggested that a limited amount of subcategories was preferred while further research was needed before adding additional subcategories.

4. Mock-ups

Mock-ups are high-fidelity designs of the web pages, including colours, fonts and images of which an example is shown in Figure 3. These mock-up pages were linked and made clickable to create a prototype which allowed for feedback on the user friendliness of the future platform while maintaining the flexibility to make adjustments after these mock-ups were presented to the consortium members during the 2021 February consortium meeting. The consortium members provided feedback which was subsequently applied to the mock-ups. Once the mock-ups had been made, adjustments were only made to the mock-ups, and not to the wireframes. The prototype created from these mock-ups provided the basis for the e-KRP user guide described in D4.3. These mock-ups can be found in Annex C.

Figure 3. An example of a mock-up screen

5. Digital style guide

The digital style guide of which an example is shown in Figure 4 is a library composed of reusable components (buttons, icons, tables, ...) that can be integrated into the different elements of the platform (e.g. web pages). The style guide has been inspired by the branding style of the overall EURAKNOS project, developed in WP5 and will be integrated in the brand platform which will insure consistent, qualitative and correct development of the platform (now and in the future), as well as for the communication and dissemination activities of the project and the platform. The digital style guide can be found in Annex D.

Figure 4. An example of an element of the digital style guide

6. Annex I: The wireframes V1

Navigation

Dashboard V1

Dashboard V2

Dashboard V3

Dashboard V4

Library Overview V1.1

The screenshot displays the EURAKNOS Library Overview V1.1 interface. On the left, a sidebar contains the EURAKNOS logo and a navigation menu with items: Dashboard, Inbox, News, Library (expanded), Thematic networks, Groups, Events, and Contribute. The Library section is further divided into three categories, each with subcategory options. The main content area is titled 'Library' and features a search bar with a magnifying glass icon and the text 'Search' and 'advanced search'. Below the search bar are filter options: Year, Media type, Language, Country, and Sort by. A grid of document cards is displayed, each with a placeholder image, a category label, a subject label, a date/time label, and an author label. The footer contains links for 'About E-KRP' and 'FAQ'.

Library Overview V1.2

Library Overview V1.3

The screenshot shows the EURAKNOS Library Overview V1.3 interface. On the left is a sidebar with the EURAKNOS logo and navigation menu items: Dashboard, Inbox, News, Library (expanded), Thematic networks, Groups, Events, and Contribute. The Library section is further divided into three categories, each with subcategory options. The main content area is titled 'Library' and features a search bar, a user profile 'Hi user', and filter options for Year, Media type, Language, Country, and Sort by. Below these are six document cards arranged in a 2x3 grid. Each card displays a placeholder image, the word 'DOCUMENT', a subject line, a date/time field, an author name, and a 'Download me' button. The bottom of the page has a footer with 'About E-KRP' and 'FAQ' links.

Library Overview V2.1

The screenshot displays the EURAKNOS Library Overview V2.1 interface. On the left, a sidebar contains the EURAKNOS logo and a navigation menu with items: Dashboard, Inbox, News, Library (expanded), Thematic networks, Groups, Events, and Contribute. The Library section is further divided into Category 1, Category 2, and Category 3, each with multiple Subcategory entries. The main content area, titled 'Library', features a search bar, filter options for Year, Media type, Language, and Country, and a 'Sort by' dropdown. Below these are several list items, each with a 'CATEGORY' header, a 'Subject' field, a paragraph of placeholder text, and an 'Author' field. A 'Date/Time' field is also present on the right side of each item. At the bottom of the page, there are links for 'About E-KRP' and 'FAQ'.

Library Overview V3.1

The screenshot displays the EURAKNOS Library Overview V3.1 interface. On the left, a navigation menu includes 'Dashboard', 'Index', 'News', 'Library', 'Thematic networks', 'Groups', 'Events', and 'Contribute'. The 'Library' section is expanded, showing three categories, each with five subcategories. The main content area is titled 'Library' and features a search bar, filter options for Year, Media type, Language, and Country, and a 'Sort by' dropdown. Below these are 10 document entries, each with a placeholder image, a category, a subject, a description, an author, and a 'Download file' button. At the bottom, there are pagination controls showing 'Previous page', '1 2 3 4 ... 10', and 'Next page', along with links for 'About E-KRP' and 'FAQ'.

- Dashboard ▾
- Inbox
- News ▾
- Library ▾
 - Category 1
 - Subcategory
 - Subcategory
 - Subcategory
 - Subcategory
 - Subcategory
 - Category 2
 - Subcategory
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 - Category 3
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 - Subcategory
- Thematic networks ▾
- Groups ▾
- Events ▾
- Contribute ▾

Article

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Related content

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Author Date/time

About e-KRP
FAQ

Library Detail Article V2

Dashboard ▾

Inbox

News ▾

Library ▲

Category 1

- Subcategory
- Subcategory
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Category 2

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Category 3

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Thematic networks ▾

Groups ▾

Events ▾

Contribute ▾

Article

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Author Download file

[About E-KRP](#) [FAQ](#)

Library Detail Feature V1

Library Detail Podcast V1

The screenshot shows a web interface for a Podcast. On the left is a navigation sidebar with the EURAKNOS logo and menu items: Dashboard, Inbox, News, Library (expanded to show Category 1, 2, and 3 with subcategories), Thematic networks, Groups, Events, and Contribute. The main content area is titled 'Podcast' and includes a search icon, a user profile 'Hi user', and a 'return to overview' link. The main heading is 'Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt'. Below this is a placeholder for an image with a play button icon. A paragraph of Lorem Ipsum text follows. There are social media icons for Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn. Another paragraph of Lorem Ipsum text is present. The 'Related content' section features three cards, each with a 'Subject' header, a 'CATEGORY' label, a small image placeholder, a paragraph of Lorem Ipsum text, and 'Author' and 'Date/Time' fields. At the bottom, there are links for 'About E-KRP' and 'FAQ'.

Library Detail Video V1

The screenshot displays the EURAKNOS web application interface for a video detail page. On the left is a navigation sidebar with the EURAKNOS logo and menu items: Dashboard, Inbox, News, Library (expanded to show Category 1, Category 2, and Category 3, each with five subcategory links), Thematic networks, Groups, Events, and Contribute. The main content area is titled 'Video' and includes a search bar with 'Hi user' and a magnifying glass icon. Below the title is a link to 'return to overview'. The video player area contains a large video player with a play button and a video icon. Below the player is a block of placeholder text: 'Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Magna sit amet purus gravida quis. Amet volutpat consequat mauris nunc congue. Nibh nisl condimentum id venenatis a condimentum vitae. Vel eros donec ac odio tempor orci. Volutpat commodo sed egestas egestas fringilla. Donec pretium vulputate sapien nec sagittis. Sollicitudin aliquam ultrices sagittis orci a scelerisque purus semper. Aliquam id diam maecenas ultricies mi eget mauris pharetra et.' Below this text are social media icons for Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn. A row of ten 'Author description' placeholders follows. The 'Related content' section features three cards, each with a 'Subject' header, a video icon, a 'CATEGORY' label, a short paragraph of placeholder text, and 'Author' and 'Date/Time' fields. At the bottom of the page are links for 'About E-KRP' and 'FAQ'.

News Detail Article V1

- Dashboard
- Inbox
- News
- Library ▼
- Thematic networks ▼
- Groups ▼
- Events ▼
- Contribute ▼

Article

[← return to News](#)

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Related content

Subject

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Author
Date/Time

About E-KRP
FAQ

- Dashboard
- Inbox
- News
- Library ▼
- Thematic networks ▼
- Groups ▼
- Events ▼
- Contribute ▼

Article

[← return to News](#)

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Related content

Subject

CATEGORY

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Author
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Author
Date/Time

[About E-KRP](#) [FAQ](#)

The EURAKNOS project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No: 817863

Page | 29

News Detail Timeline V1

- Dashboard
- Inbox
- News
- Library ▼
- Thematic networks ▼
- Groups ▼
- Events ▼
- Contribute ▼

Timeline

← return to News

TITLE TOPIC

- Title article**
13 April 2019

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- Title article**
11 April 2019

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- Title article**
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- Title article**
3 April 2019

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- START**
1 April 2019

Facebook Twitter LinkedIn

Related content

Subject

CATEGORY

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AuthorDate/Time

Subject

CATEGORY

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AuthorDate/Time

Subject

CATEGORY

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AuthorDate/Time

About E-KRP FAQ

Thematic Networks Overview V1

The screenshot displays the EURAKNOS web application interface for 'Thematic networks'. On the left is a navigation sidebar with the EURAKNOS logo and menu items: Dashboard, Inbox, News, Library, Thematic networks (expanded), Groups, Events, and Contribute. The main content area is titled 'Thematic networks' and features a search bar. Below the search bar is a grid of 17 thematic network cards, each with a logo and name: 4D4F, AFINET, AGRISPIN, AGRI FOR VALOR, CERERE, EU PIG, EUFRIH, EURODAIRY, FERTINNOWA, HENNOVATION, HNV LINK, INNO 4 GRASS, OK NET ARABLE, SHEEP NET, SKIN, SMART AKIS, and WINETWORK. At the bottom of the interface are links for 'About E-KRP' and 'FAQ'.

Thematic Networks Detail V1

About e-KRP V1

About e-KRP V2

About e-KRP V3

7. Annex II: The wireframes V2

Landing page (not logged in)

Navigation: sector (not logged in)

Navigation: themes (not logged in)

Category page (not logged in)

Content page: Practice abstract (not logged in)

The screenshot displays the FARMBOOK website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the FARMBOOK logo, a search bar, and links for 'About', 'Help', 'Log in', and 'EN0'. Below the navigation bar, the main content area features a large header for 'The Ideal Thematic Network' with a placeholder image. The article text is a placeholder using Lorem Ipsum. Below the article, there is a section for 'Practice abstract' with a 'Read more...' button. A comment section follows, showing 11 comments and options to 'Share', 'Save', and 'React'. A login prompt is present: 'Log in or sign up to leave a comment'. Below the comments, there are two user avatars: 'Peter S' (verified user, 6 hours ago) and 'Laurens W' (verified user, 12 minutes ago). At the bottom of the main content area, there is a 'Related posts from Peter' section with three post thumbnails and titles: 'Vestibulum id ligula porta felis euismod', 'Solicitudin Elit Purus Fusce', and 'Ipsum Magna Etiam Tristique Risus'. The footer contains a grid of links under 'ABOUT US', 'OUR COMMUNITY', and 'OUR SOCIALS', along with the FARMBOOK logo, copyright information, and a European Union flag.

Content page: Podcast (not logged in)

Content page: Video (not logged in)

The screenshot shows a web interface for 'FARMBOOK'. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home', 'About', 'Help', and 'Logout' options. The main content area features a post titled 'The ideal Thematic Network' by a user named 'Peter B'. The post includes a video player with a play button. Below the video, there are social media interaction icons for comments, shares, likes, and reports. A comment section follows, showing a comment from 'Laurens W.' and a reply from 'Peter B.'. At the bottom of the post, there is a 'Related posts from Peter' section with three thumbnails and titles: 'Vestibulum id ligula porta felis euismod', 'Sed ut perspiciatis unde omnis iste natus error sit voluptatem accusantium doloremque laudantium', and 'Ipsum Magna Eliam Tristique Risus'. The footer contains 'ABOUT US', 'OUR COUNTRIES', and 'OUR SOCIALS' sections, along with the FARMBOOK logo and copyright information.

Community page (not logged in)

The screenshot shows the 'Community' page of the FARMBOOK website. The page is titled 'FORESTRY' and features a navigation menu with options like 'Precision', 'Actors', 'Systems', 'Types', 'Infrastructures', 'Tools', 'Technologies', and 'Community'. A search bar is located at the top right. The main content area displays a list of experts, each with a profile picture, name, email address, and a short bio. The experts listed are: Laurena Vdc, Jaylen Press, Miracle Bator, Duke Calzoni, Alfredo Saria, and James Septimus. Each expert's bio is a placeholder text. The page also includes a sidebar for filtering experts, a pagination control at the bottom, and a footer with 'ABOUT US', 'OUR COMMUNITY', and 'OUR SOCIALS' sections.

Search results page: List view (not logged in)

The screenshot displays the FARMBOOK search results page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the FARMBOOK logo, 'Sector', 'Themes', and 'Advanced search' options. On the right, there are links for 'About', 'Help', 'Log in', and 'EN0'. The main content area shows a search for 'Yearbook Pork 2019-2020' with 100 results. The left sidebar contains filters for Media type (Document, Spreadsheet, Podcast, Video), Country (All, United Kingdom, France, Spain, The Netherlands), Language (All, French, Spanish, Dutch, English), and Year (1999-2019). The search results are displayed in a list view, sorted by relevance. Each result includes a thumbnail, the title 'Yearbook Pork 2019-2020', a duration of 66 min, and interaction options like '11 comments', 'Share', and 'Save'. The footer contains navigation links for 'ABOUT US', 'OUR COMMUNITY', and 'OUR SOCIALS', along with copyright information and a European Union flag.

Search results page: Tile view (not logged in)

FARMBOOK Sector Themes Advanced search About Help Log in ENG ▼

FORESTRY: Practices Actors Systems Types Infrastructures Tools Technologies Community

Filter your search:

Media type
 Document
 Pdf
 Spreadsheet
 Podcast
 Video

Country
 All
 United Kingdom
 France
 Spain
 The Netherlands

Show more:

Language
 All
 French
 Spanish
 Dutch
 English

Show more:

Year
 1000 — 2020

More filters

188 results Sort by relevance

Fusce parturient dapibus
 Tr Quick news • 8 min
 ★ 7
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 Tr Podcast • 66 min
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 Tr Video • 66 min
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Venenatis cursus mollis
 Tr Quick news • 8 min
 ★ 7
 Nullam quis risus eget urna mollis ornare vel eu leo. Donec ullamcorper nulla non metus auctor fringilla.

Ipsum risus sit cras
 Tr Quick news • 8 min
 ★ 7
 Donec id elit non mi porta gravida at eget metus. Cras mattis consectetur purus sit.

Pellentesque Mollis Vulputate Eit Sollicitudin
 Tr Quick news • 8 min
 ★ 7
 Aenean eu leo quam. Pellentesque ornare sem lacinia quam venenatis vestibulum.

Fusce parturient dapibus
 Tr Podcast • 66 min
 ★ 7
 Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Curabitur blandit tempus porttitor.

Nullam mollis egestas
 Tr Video • 66 min
 ★ 7
 Praesent commodo cursus magna, vel scelerisque nisl consectetur et. Cras mattis consectetur purus sit.

Mattis ridiculus fermentum
 Tr Podcast • 66 min
 ★ 7
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1 2 3 4 ... 8

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 Support
 Contact us

OUR COMMUNITY
 Blog
 Networks
 Meetings & activities
 Learn (journal)

OUR SOCIALS
 Facebook
 Twitter
 Instagram

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Mobile Landing page (not logged in)

Mobile Navigation: Level 1 (not logged in)

Mobile Navigation: Level 2 (not logged in)

Mobile Navigation: Level 3 (not logged in)

Mobile Content page: content (not signed in)

Mobile Content page: info (not signed in)

← Overview

Yearbook pork 2019-2020

Video • 68 min

Video **Info** Discussion

Contact information of the authors:
By Laurens Van der Cruyssen
Leap Forward Group (Belgium)
laurens.vandercruyssen@leapforward.be

Keywords:
Podcast Forestry Thematic network

Link to website: www.euraknos.eu

Related content

- **Forestry podcast**
Podcast • 66 min
- **Lorem Nibh**
Quick news • 8 min
- **Mollis Egestas Porta**
Video • 68 min

 FARMBOOK

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Mobile Content page: discussion (not signed in)

← Overview

Yearbook pork 2019-2020

Video • 68 min

Video • Info • **Discussion**

Pieter S • verified user
3 days ago
19

Vestibulum id ligula porta felis euismod semper. Nullam id dolor id nibh ultricies vehicula ut id elit. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Sed posuere consectetur est at... [read more](#)

Laurens Vdc • verified user
6 hours ago
1

Great podcast!

9 more replies

Related content

- **Forestry podcast**
Podcast • 66 min
- **Lorem Nibh**
Quick news • 8 min
- **Mollis Egestas Porta**
Video • 68 min

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8. Annex III: The mock-ups

Landing page (not logged in)

Navigation (not logged in)

Category page: Forestry (not logged in)

Category page: crop farming (not logged in)

Category page: Livestock (not logged in)

Category page: Environment (not logged in)

Category page: Society (not logged in)

Category page: Economics (not logged in)

Content page: Article (not logged in)

Categories Search About Help 1,155 IN EN

RETURN TO OVERVIEW 304 News 4 0 comment 0

The title of this interesting article

January 12, 2019
By Joseph Stevens, Katherine Youth and Forest adriament
Smart-Axis

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"LOREM IPSUM DOLOR SIT AMET, CONSECUTUR ADIPISCING ELIT, SED DO EUISMOD TEMPOR INCIDIDUNT UT LABORE ET DOLORE MAGNA ALIQUA. UT ENIM AD MINIM VENIAM, QUIS NOSTRUD EXERCITATION ULLAMCO LABORIS NISI UT ALIQUIP EX EA COMMODUO CONSEQUAT. DUIS AUTE IRURE DOLOR IN REPREHENDIT IN VOLUPTATE VELIT ESSE CILLUM DOLOR EU FUGIAT NULLA PARIATUR. EXCEPTUR SINT OCCAECAT CUPIDATAT NON PROIDENT, SUNT IN CULPA QUI OFFICIA DESERUNT MOLLIT ANIM ID EST LABORUM."

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Categories: [AMAZON](#) [AZUL](#) [BLAUW](#)

Lag in or sign up to leave a comment [Log in](#) [Sign up](#)

Related content

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0 TEXT - 11 MIN
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Directions
Contact us and more maps

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Content page: Podcast (not logged in)

The screenshot shows a website interface for a podcast article. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Categories', a search bar, and 'About Help' links. The main article is titled 'The title of this interesting article' and is dated January 12, 2019, by Joseph Stevens, Katherine Youth, and Forest Johnson. The article text is a placeholder, and a video player shows a field of wheat. Below the article, there are three comments from users Elsie Johnson, Donald Mc., and Tom Jacobs. At the bottom, a 'Related content' section features three article cards with images of hands holding soil, a wheat field, and red apples.

Content page: Video (not logged in)

Community page: Overview (not logged in)

Community page: Detail (not logged in)

The screenshot shows a web interface for a community page titled "Forestry". At the top, there is a navigation bar with "Categories", "Search", "About", "Help", and a user profile icon. Below the navigation is a large image of a forest with the word "Forestry" overlaid. A search bar is positioned below the image. Underneath, there are tabs for "All content", "Community", and "Experts". The main content area features a post titled "Best way to implement this technique?" by Joseph Brown, dated 2 days ago. The post has 100 likes and 55 comments. Below the post, there are three comments from users: Elin Johnson (3 days ago), David M., and Tom Jacobs (7 days ago). Each comment includes a placeholder text and interaction icons for likes and replies. At the bottom of the page, there is a footer with the EURAKNOS logo, contact information, social media links (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram), and a list of services (About, Help and FAQs, Support, Contact us). The footer also includes copyright information for 2020 EURAKNOS and links to the website, privacy policy, and cookies.

Experts page: Overview (not logged in)

Experts page: Detail author (not logged in)

Experts page: Detail organisation (not logged in)

Search results: general list view (not logged in)

The screenshot displays a search results page for a web application. The page layout includes a header with a logo, navigation links, and a search bar. The main content area shows a list of search results, each with a placeholder image, a title, a description, and a list of tags. The results are filtered by 'FARMBOON' and 'YOUR FARMBOON'. The page also includes a sidebar with active filters and category/subcategory options. At the bottom, there is a footer with contact information, social media links, and a copyright notice.

Search results: general tile view (not logged in)

Search results: Category list view (not logged in)

Contact page (not logged in)

Categories Search About Help R. (30/10) EN

GET IN CONTACT WITH US

Contact

Donec ullamcorper nulla non metus auctor fringilla. Quis vel elit tempus ornare. Aenean eu leo quam. Pellentesque ornare sem lacinia quam venenatis vestibulum. Maecenas sed diam eget risus varius blandit sit amet nunc nisl. Curabitur blandit porttitor enim. Morbi leo auctor a, hendrerit quis velit. Vivamus magna justo, lacinia eget consectetur sed, convallis at tellus. Donec rutrum congue leo eget malesuada. Donec enim diam lectus. Vestibulum quis lorem vel libero, lobortis vel enim. Donec eu sapien eu erat tristique euismod. Nullam quis elit sit amet nulla auctor convallis. Quis vel elit tempus ornare. Aenean eu leo quam. Pellentesque ornare sem lacinia quam venenatis vestibulum. Donec rutrum congue leo eget malesuada. Donec enim diam lectus. Vestibulum quis lorem vel libero, lobortis vel enim. Donec eu sapien eu erat tristique euismod. Nullam quis elit sit amet nulla auctor convallis.

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E-mail address

Message

Send

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Show map
Contact details
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Privacy policy page (not logged in)

Mobile Category page: Content (not logged in)

Mobile navigation: Level 1 (not logged in)

Mobile navigation: Level 2 (not logged in)

Mobile Search filter: Level 1 (not logged in)

Mobile Search filter: Level 1 (not logged in)

✕

Active filters

🌿 FORESTRY ✕

Categories ▼

Subcategories ▼

Media type ▼

Language ▼

Published ▼

Show results

9. Annex IV: The digital style guide

Overview

Fundamentals: Colors

Fundamentals: Typography

Name	Font-size / Line-height	Letter spacing	Font	Style
Header-1	58px / 58px	0px	Poppins	Exchange knowledge
Header-2	48px / 54px	0px	Poppins	Exchange knowledge
Header-3	30px / 42px	0px	Poppins	Exchange knowledge
Header-4	24px / 32px	0px	Poppins	Titel of the article
Header-5	14px / 20px	3px	Poppins	EXCHANGE KNOWLEDGE
Header-6	14px / 20px	3px	Roboto	Threads & discussions
Capo-big	12px / 24px	3px	Roboto	EXCHANGE KNOWLEDGE
Capo-small	10px / 24px	3px	Roboto	EXCHANGE KNOWLEDGE
Body-big	18px / 26px	0px	Roboto	Exchange knowledge
Body	16px / 26px	0px	Roboto	Exchange knowledge
Body-small	14px / 20px	0px	Roboto	Exchange knowledge

Fundamentals: Iconography

Buildings blocks: Buttons

Buildings blocks: Tags

Buildings blocks: UI elements

Components: Navigation

Components: Footer

Components: Content

Components: Community

